

Project Leadership and Performance of Housing Projects in Machakos County: A Case Study of Mavoko Sub-County

^{1*}Justus Muli

¹MDS Student: Management University of Africa
P. O. Box. 1255-00521, Nairobi, Kenya

^{2*}Dr. Juster Nyaga

²Management University of Africa
P. O. Box. 29677-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

Corresponding Author: ^{1*}Justus Muli, ^{2*}Dr. Juster Nyaga

Abstract:- Objective was to examine project leadership and performance of housing projects in Mavoko Machakos and goal was to establish the effects of project funding, and project planning on the performance of housing projects. Results will aid in building the framework for further study and provide a critical analysis of project leadership techniques and housing project performance. Resource-based view, Goal-Setting, and Contingency Theory are the theoretical pillars and descriptive design was adopted with 200 persons as a target group. A sample size of 100 people was chosen using stratified random selection. Questionnaires were used to gather data. A pilot study was conducted using 10 employees who were randomly selected from the target population and SPSS were used to analyze data. Data is presented on the data. The finding showed that the performance of housing projects is significantly influenced by project finance, according to the study, which found that this factor is statistically significant, and project planning significantly affects the performance and study suggests that the national and county governments include stakeholders in their project financing efforts since project finance has a substantial impact on how well housing projects will perform. The performance of housing projects would be improved since the stakeholder's viewpoint would be significant in terms of financiers.

Keywords:- Project Leadership, Performance of Housing Projects, Project Funding, Project Planning, Housing Projects.

I. BACKGROUND

Intense competition makes it very challenging for businesses, organizations, and higher education institutions to compete with and surpass their rivals in the majority of industries. Institutions should acquire a competitive edge to outperform rivals (Zehir, Can, & Karaboga, 2016). To gain such a competitive edge and higher performance, several strategies can be applied (Obeidat, Al-Suradi, Masa'deh, & Tarhini, 2016). According to Masa'deh, Tarhini, Al-Dmour, and Obeidat (2018), organizations work to increase performance by creating and putting into action business strategies that take advantage of market possibilities while

leveraging available resources and skills. The structure, the activities, the investments, the relationship to the market, and the commercial success of a company can all be significantly impacted by its strategy. A problem-solving instrument that simultaneously develops new skills and enhances performance is a strategy (Grant, 2016). Assembling specialized assets, and spotting opportunities to offer customers providing those goods and services for increased profits while providing quality products in the marketplace are all made possible by a strategy (Al-Ansari, Bederr, & Chen, 2015). However, not all businesses adapt to environmental changes in the same manner.

➤ Project Performance

According to Nel and Beudeker (2015), project performance helps firms maximize revenues, reduce the impact of unforeseen and competitive events on project objectives, and exploit opportunities when they arise. The primary project performance metrics are cost, time, and quality because they are the foundational components of a successful project. The term "quality" refers to all of the characteristics that a product must possess to satisfy customer's needs and be useful. The specification of quality requirements should expressly ensure the efficacy and conformity of quality performance. Since small and medium-sized businesses prioritize making a profit over project investment, Cost, time, quality, and profitability are used to evaluate the success of a project. Kalia and Bhardwaj (2019) define a program's performance as the extent to which it achieves the predetermined goals, taking into account time, quality, budget, security, and, generally speaking, customer satisfaction. According to Nel and Beudeker (2015), critical The performance of the software is a factor in figuring out whether a project is successful If a program can reach its goals and remain viable after that, it can be considered successful. Internationally, various businesses have been lamenting the countless program performances that fall short of the intended outcome and the lost money. The satisfaction of program participants must be balanced with the benefits to the company. Concern among clients in the public and private sectors is thought to begin as program performance gets closer to expectations (Ellis, et al., 2022).

➤ *Project Funding*

It is impossible to overstate the significance of project funding. According to Oyeyipo et al. (2016), associations are not autonomous entities that act solely on their own free will. As opposed to that, they are constantly interacting with other entities within the context of asset trade connections. Lack of funding and uncertainty force organizations to adapt to the requirements of crucial project funding suppliers. However, obtaining those funds frequently necessitates sacrificing ownership interests and decision-making authority (Wasserman, 2014). Therefore, organizations need to strike a balance between ownership and value. This is accomplished by maintaining multiple sources of supply, forming joint ventures, integrating vertically with suppliers, and integrating horizontally with rivals and markets (Hatch, 2013). The majority of the time, assets include various forms of funding, skills, authoritative practices, data, and learning that contribute to improved hierarchical proficiency and viability. Mwathi (2019) performed a study to find out whether funding sources affect real estate growth. Equity and venture money were found to be the least often employed kinds of funding, with mortgage finance being the most common. The findings indicated that mortgage financing and real estate development have a significant positive link and that between 2016 and 2021, mortgage financing rose steadily as a consequence of the diversity of products offered by mortgage businesses and the low-interest rates on their loans.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

An important factor in determining project's success is the best practices for project management, especially housing projects. However, obstacles still exist, making it challenging to develop effective project management techniques, which has resulted in several failed projects (Kariungi, 2019). Numerous housing projects in the Mavoko sub-county have stalled, which has hurt the number of homes available in Athi River, Syiokimau, Katani, and other areas. Due to funding issues, land disputes, or decisions made by residents (stakeholders), 50% of housing projects that were started during the 2017–2018 fiscal year have come to an end. Twenty per cent of those projects have not yet started (Cytonn, 2020). The county's plan to provide new, suitable, and affordable housing in urban areas will fail if these issues are not resolved. An economic survey (2021) reveals that despite the scourge of COVID-19, the building and construction sector also experienced a slowed growth of 6.3% in 2018 compared to an increased growth of 8.5% in 2017, a further decline to 5.6% was recorded in 2019, and an increase in growth of 11.8% in 2020. The performance of the industry has remained below the 9% targeted rate due to the erratic growth rate of the construction sector. These projects' subpar performance has been linked to inadequate leadership, management, and decision-making. Many construction projects experience cost overruns, which prevents them from satisfying the needs of investors, governments, or people, as the case may be (Munywa, 2021).

Mungai (2017) looked at the difficulties in housing development and sustainability for the low-income market.

He identified issues like the difficult land acquisition procedure, high transaction costs in comparison to income, and out-of-date planning. Wanjohi and Mugure (2018) found that construction companies have implemented project risk management strategies to reduce project delays, overruns, and failures. The study fills this contextual gap. The study suggests that a study of this kind be carried out using various setups to fill an empirical gap. Brandon & Lombardi's (2017) study, evaluating sustainable development in the built environment, sustainable development is conceptualized in a variety of ways, primarily about environmental concerns, social, economic, and political developments, and the long-term advantages of maintaining created assets. Among all previous research topics, It has not been explored effect of project management on housing performance in Mavoko sub-county. In this study, the Mavoko sub-county housing project was examined to evaluate project management and performance.

➤ *Objectives*

- To determine how project funding affects the Mavoko Sub-County housing projects' performance.
- To investigate how project planning affects Mavoko Sub-County housing projects' performance.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

➤ *Resource-Based View*

In 1959, Penrose established this theory, but Wernerfelt's work in 1984 helped make it more widely known for its applicability in analyzing business success (Kozlenkova, et al, 2014). Wernerfelt claimed that the internal resources of the company are the true drivers of its performance and profitability. The phrase "RBV" generally refers to the viewpoint that believes in resources. This early understanding of the resource-based view is attributed to Penrose's research from that year (Kozlenkova, Samaha, & Palmatier, 2014). These resources are arranged so that they are thought of as internal resources that the company already has. The RBV viewpoint's advantages were furthered by Jay Barney, whose work has since gained traction. He outlined the key internal resource characteristics and their connection to competitive advantages, a company has a competitive advantage when it can increase the economic worth of its nearest competition in a certain market (Kozlenkova, et al, 2014). A transient competitive advantage and a long-term competitive advantage were separated in later publications. According to Gills, Combs, and Ketchen (2014), not all organizational resources are necessary they must produce a competitive advantage. An organization's wealth must be challenging to duplicate, replace, or transfer for them to reach the position where they can generate profits. According to Gills, Combs, and Ketchen (2014), The ability to employ company resources, which are inventories of immediately usable components possessed by the firm, differs from the corporation's competencies. The features and forms of resources that generate an edge, higher performance, and competitive advantage are all components of the RBV theory (Gillis, et al, 2014).

Kozlenkova, (2014), RBV refers to the use of a variety of a firm's accessible tangible and intangible resources. These resources must be diverse for any company to convert its organizational strategy into a lasting economic gain. The RBV clarifies how a business can outperform its competitors. The RBV theory places a focus on the organization's internal resources when implementing its strategy. RBV theory proponents like Jensen, et al (2016) contend that for businesses to perform better, it is preferable to repurpose current resources as opposed to trying to acquire new resources or skills for every opportunity. There are two categories of these resources. According to the theory, a company must identify its special resources and decide where to use them to maximize profits. RBV also contends that cost leadership strategies are important performance indicators that enhance a company's competitiveness and performance and can establish and preserve an economic gain (Hitt, et al, 2016).

Although core resources are significant drivers of organizational performance, the RBV theory is constrained by its exclusive emphasis on the internal environment as a means of maximizing a company's superior performance (Gillis, Combs, & Ketchen, 2014). The RBV has an external environment that impacts the performance and competitive advantage of the company. The truth is that outside factors have an equal impact on how a firm performs in the market. External variables, such as rules and regulations, taxation, sectoral policies, and compliance procedures, have an impact on how enterprises function in the market. When examining elements that can influence the strategies it can use, external resources must also be taken into account. To study strategies that produce superior performance, it is vital to consider both external factors and a firm's internal resources, as suggested by theory (Hitt, et al, 2016). Despite its flaws, the theory is chosen as a supplementary concept. The RBV is still a crucial principle for describing how a firm can use the instruments available to it for enhancing performance, and for this study, the variables that are supported by this theory include project planning and project funding.

➤ *Contingency Theory*

Hofer was the pioneer in the field of strategic management who promoted His work in 1975 and launched the theory and first managerial applications of these theories. According to writers like Ginsberg and Venkatraman (1985), the discipline of organization management has seen a substantial increase in the use of contingency theory since Hofer's work. Ginsberg and Venkatraman (1985) make a distinction between two perspectives on strategy: one that believes it to be a reaction to the environment and the other as a component that directly influences performance in various contexts (both internal and external). It is frequently stated that contingency theory supports the stance by avoiding a preference According to the study, "there is no best way of organizing a firm, the appropriate form depends on the nature of the firm's task environment," whether internal resources or the external environment are the main element that affects performance. be a result, theory has been

referred to be a mid-range theory that concentrates on detecting (Volberda, Weerdt, Verwaal, Stienstra, & Verdu, 2004).

It is possible to identify contingent linkages produced by the interplay of a firm's internal resources and the surrounding environment by assessing how a selected approach performs in various circumstances. To attain greater performance, a strategy must consider both the internal and external settings for it to be successful. Pearce and Robinson concur with this position, believing that how businesses strike the correct balance between utilizing the current resources and reacting to environmental changes determines the success of a plan (Kruger et al, 2002). Organizational strategies, in the words of Pearce and Robinson, "must be based on determining an appropriate 'fit' relationship between the organization's objective, adjustments to its internal and external resources, and the level of its core competencies" (Kruger et al, 2002). The theory is advantageous because it informs the investigation's goals. RBV and goal-setting are enhanced by the contingency theory. It strengthens the basis for, project planning, as well as superior housing project performance.

➤ *Goal-Setting Theory*

Kurt Lewin's early findings on degrees of aspiration served as the foundation for this idea, which was later developed by Dr. Edwin Locke, who started looking into it in the 1480s (Locke & Latham, 2010). The planned result of a task or activity is something that a person intentionally hopes to achieve or get. To attain desired results, setting objectives requires the intentional act of selecting performance standards (Latham, 2010). This goal-setting strategy views the desire and purpose to attain a goal as the source of motivation. The theorists identified coercive, normative, and mimetic pressures that determine the operational direction of an organization. Further analysis indicates that coercive pressures emerge from resource-dominant organizations, whereas the coercive aspect captures the product price and the normative dimension focuses on the aspect of lead time (Hovav,2017).

The hardest goal lines are difficult to complete within the organization's time constraints and serve as a point of reference for determining satisfaction and dissatisfaction. When establishing goals is done to evaluate personal performance, it suggests that a person's aspirations must ensure that their basic requirements are addressed, such as adequate pay and a secure environment, to foster an atmosphere that will enable them to achieve their potential (Ferris, 2007). He claims that goal-setting is a collection of decision-theoretical frameworks for understanding motivation and productivity. People respond well to results, both positive and bad, according to the two major concepts of goal-setting theory, and they perceive the worries that result from their interactions with others and the causal links between the outcomes (Amit & Livnat, 2008). According to this notion, two expectations motivate people to perform. Identifying the likelihood that an effort will always result in the desired performance is the first stage in theory. The likelihood that a certain performance leads to intended

results is the subject of the second goal-setting step. Although certain efforts won't be recognized, the employee won't be motivated to finish a particular assignment.

This study adopts this theory which seeks to examine how certain factors affect a housing project's success such as project funding, and project planning, which are influenced by external and internal factors that are deemed acceptable in the organization set up. The theory indicates that firms become the same due to pressure for authenticity which shows that firms that deal with similar products are inclined to ever-changing customers' needs that force these organizations to copy their competitors that are leading in the same sector (Gauthier, 2013). The theory also focuses on organizational social behaviour that outlines formations, customs, and procedures as organization strategies (Aksom & Tymchenko, 2020).

The theory provides a framework that is used in analyzing how organizations interact with their employees and other players, and how it can be entrenched over time. The theory is still applicable in modern organization strategies, procedures; structures as well and policies as organizations interact with various players in their surroundings, this affects how organizations determine their performance in competitive and stormy surroundings. The theory was adopted by the study for its explanation of the changes brought about in the performance of housing projects that are influenced by project funding, and project planning, which are deemed acceptable in the organization set-up. This study used this theory on the applicable areas that affected technology adopted, organizational policies, management strategies, structures, and procedures in the organization and showed the way they are entrenched as the organization interacts with its surroundings that affect deliverables of housing projects.

➤ *Project Funding and Performance of Projects*

In Karachi, Khan, Abdul-Rasid, Bardai, and Saruchi (2020) investigated the structure of affordable cooperative housing using a cutting-edge waqf-based source of funding. With the aim of creating a harmonious coexistence of cooperative and waqf housing initiatives, a novel framework known as the waqf cooperative housing framework. Interviews were used to acquire primary information and analyzed with the help of the NVIVO software. The interviewees included CEOs, senior executives of Islamic financial institutions, and government officials, scholars, community leaders, and managers from the real estate development sector. It was discovered that cutting-edge strategies like affordable housing in Karachi is a problem that WCHF can solve in a variety of ways, including easing the financial burden on the public purse, enhancing the conditions of the disadvantaged and maintaining corporate social responsibility of real estate developers maintaining the moral obligations that people in general and condo owners have to one another, and generating new employment opportunities for those who are already employed. The study suggests similar studies be conducted in other areas, and this creates a methodological and

contextual gap that can be filled by researching the current study.

In Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, Alharbi (2022) looked at a preliminary analysis of COVID-19's implications on funding for affordable housing. There aren't many studies looking into how the COVID-19 pandemic might actually reduce the likelihood that everyone will have access to affordable housing by 2030. Delphi approach was used to evaluate the viewpoints of officials, businesspeople, academics, and workers. The SA Vision 2030 plan reflects an exceptional country in every way, according to the findings and including providing citizens with financing for affordable housing. SA's Vision 2030 is under jeopardy due to COVID-19 outbreak for financing housing, according to the findings. Covidian-19's perceived effects on the financing housing include the rising housing costs, increased foreclosures and evictions, a growing housing shortage, potential homelessness, strategies to improvements in payment relief, to encourage affordable housing. Researching the current study can fill a methodological and contextual gap that is created by the study's suggestion that related research be done in other fields.

Mwathi and Karanja (2017) looked into Kenya's real estate financing options. The study specifically examined whether mortgage financing, real estate funding can come from stock, savings, and venture capital investment. Research used a descriptive approach. All of Nairobi's real estate businesses made up the study's sample. For five years, secondary data were used in this study. Frequency tables and charts were created using SPSS to examine the data used to present the findings. After that, descriptive statistics like frequencies, means, to assess the data, percentages were utilized. According to the study, equity and venture capital are the least used forms of financing, with mortgage financing being the most popular. The results also showed that mortgage financing and real estate development have a very positive relationship. If businesses want equity and venture capital to be a more important source of funding, they will need to market, the report claims. Equity and venture capital finance may only be a dependable source of funding when combined with other forms of funding. By recommending study on the implications of financing sources amid unstable political situations, a global economic crisis, and unfavourable economic conditions, the selection of finance sources for real estate enterprises in Kenya, as well as other internal and external considerations, the study fills a gap and, this study will fill the gap.

➤ *Project Planning and Performance of Projects*

Iskandarani, Proverbs, and Xiao (2022) looked into ways to enhance the theoretical foundation for creating and organizing post-conflict home rehabilitation initiatives. By building cooperative methods at the early design phases and the tasks essential to achieving successful outcomes with the assistance of relief groups., In order to overcome the flaws of current home reconstruction models in post-conflict situations, a conceptual framework is constructed utilizing a synthesis of this literature. The results show the critical shortcomings and faults in the present house rehabilitation

models. For post-conflict home rebuilding, a framework has been developed to enhance collaborative design and planning methodologies and practices. Current study will fill a methodological gap provided by this study.

Abdullah and Alshibani’s (2022) investigation towards a multi-criteria decision-making framework for selecting sustainable commercial partners for Saudi Arabian housing projects. In the study, is created that takes into account standards from a thorough literature search and advice from industry experts obtained through survey, with more polls including decision-making techniques The findings revealed criteria broken down into four groups of managers, along with their sub-groups. Based on the experts' subjective assessments, study indicated that the key factors were rather closely connected in significance, with the technical criteria tied at 27%, the management criteria at 13%, and the other categories at 4% criteria coming in second at 24%, and the financial criteria coming in third at 22%. The study provides an empirical and contextual gap from a middle east perspective that needs to examine from a local perspective.

Rashidi, Yong, Maxwell, and Fang (2022) looked at construction planning using virtual reality that was based on 4D BIM. By combining construction industry experts use virtual reality and 4D building information modelling to design projects with light steel frame, this study seeks to unearth novel experimental findings. The traditional approach required the participants to complete tasks related to construction planning for the targeted project using conventional platforms, construction designs on paper, as well as their physical visualization. The same tasks must be completed by participants using more advanced platforms, such as virtual reality environments and 4D building information modeling and the outcomes showed that 4D building information modeling improved Usability has increased by 10.3%, accuracy has increased by 89.1%, and speed has increased by 30% with virtual reality in comparison to the traditional paper-based method. A paired t-test is also used to confirm the results, and it is supported by the consistency of the results. This study suggests that using contemporary methods and technologies will improve construction planning. These results have significant implications for the global construction sector, which is struggling with low productivity issues, delays, and uncertainty regarding building delivery timelines as a result of inadequate construction planning.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of the descriptive study design was to describe behaviour without in any way modifying it. Before applying quantitative research designs, the design is typically used to find useful cues about the variables that will be examined (Bordens & Abbott, 2017). Since the primary goal of the research study is typically to gain a deeper understanding of the research study, a quantitative research design was used, thus the findings should be able to be used across a wide range of institutions. The researcher targets all housing projects in Mavoko Sub-County between 2013- 2020. According to the Ministry of Housing, there are 200 funded housing projects in Machakos County. The target population of this survey were 200 project managers of housing projects in the county.

The study used stratified random sampling, which Creswell and Creswell (2018) found to be objective and give all populations an equal chance of being chosen. stratified random sampling was used, which Creswell and Creswell (2018) found to be objective and give the entire population an equal chance of being chosen. Kothari and Garg (2015), a sample is the division used in representing a large unit to reflect the features of the population. Cooper and Schindler (2018) noted that to prevent biases, the study sample size should be random and 1-10% of the target population is regarded as a suitable size, according to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill's (2018) recommendation. This study adopted 10% of the target population of 1100 which is 110 participants.

Questionnaires are preferred by the researcher since the study that has used them and questionnaires are recommended to be economical and they are easily administered as well as time-saving (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2018). Questionnaires are considered to be cheaper instruments of data collection and the researcher can obtain volumes, however, noted that the questionnaire's only disadvantage is cannot be administered to illiterate respondents not able to read and write (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The researcher used questionnaires because it makes it possible and easy for correlation, descriptive, and inferential statistical analysis as echoed by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2018). These inquiries will also effectively contribute to the enrichment of the qualitative methodology. Since most respondents would prefer not to have their identities revealed, the questionnaire further ensures anonymity. Primary data was collected using questionnaires while secondary data used in the literature review.

SPSS and basic statistics were used to analyze the qualitative data. The raw data gathered from the field was coded before the generalization of the findings was made. Tables were used to present the results and analyze them using descriptive statistics. The relationship between the study variables was demonstrated using inferential statistics. The investigation made use of the Pearson correlation matrix. The use of Pearson correlation allowed for the prediction and description of the relationship between the

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

direction and magnitude of the variables. A 2-tailed test with a significance level of 5% was used to conduct the correlation test. To reveal the full model significance, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. The calculated f statistic was compared with the tabulated f statistic. A critical p-value of 0.05 was used to determine whether the overall model was significant or not.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Sample consisted of 100 people and 86 respondents responded, reflecting an 86% response rate, while 14% did not complete the questionnaires. The response rate to the

research study was quite high. As sported by Kothari and Garg (2015), Male project manager’s majority. The majority were grouped between 31 and 35 years old, 40 and 45 years old, then 36 and 39 years old and the majority of respondents claimed they had worked for six to ten years.

To determine whether each of the independent variables in this study that is project funding, project, and project planning influences the performance of housing projects, a bivariate linear analysis was carried out between structural arrangements and the performance of housing projects.

Table 1 Model Summary for Project Funding

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.632 ^a	.399	.394	.60908

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project funding

Table 1 shows the performance of housing projects with project funding performing the dual roles of predictor and dependent variable. Project funding and housing project success are linked, according to the regression analysis, which showed R = 0.632 suggested a substantial positive association., and R² = 0.399 implies that a unit change in project funding may explain 39.9% of the variance in housing project performance and other elements that were not included in the research to 60.1 percent.

Table 2 ANOVA^a for Project Funding

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	27.875	1	27.875	75.141	.000 ^b
1 Residual	41.920	85	.371		
Total	69.796	86			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of housing projects
b. Predictors: (Constant), Project funding

As shown in Table 2, the values of F = 75.141 suggest that project funding has a substantial influence on how effective housing projects are, proving that the model fits the data well and that project funding affects how well housing projects perform in Mavoko Sub-county. Regression model significant predictor of the dependent variable with a significance level of 0.000, less than 0.05. Table 2 summarizes findings.

Table 3 Regression Coefficients^a for Project Funding

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.095	.331		3.309	.001	.439	1.751
Project funding	.688	.079	.632	8.668	.000	.531	.845

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of housing projects
Performance of housing projects = 1.095 + .688 (Project funding)

Table 3 shows that Mavoko Sub-County's project funding has a significant positive impact on the performance of housing projects. According to the data, project funding has a strong link with p0.05 for performance (P = 0.01). A rise in the mean index of project funding should improve the performance of housing projects by 688 units (68.8%), according to the statistical significance of the value of project financing (t = 8.668, p.05). The regression model behind Table 3's findings is as follows: performance of housing projects = 1.095 + 0.688 (project funding). The model demonstrates that project funding has an impact on the Performance of housing projects in Mavoko Sub-county.

Table 4 Model Summary for Project Planning

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.575 ^a	.331	.325	.64274

a. (Constant), Project planning

Project planning served as the predictor factor in a regression analysis with housing project performance serving as the dependent variable. Project planning and the success of housing projects are fundamentally tied, according to regression analysis, which found a relationship with $R = 0.575$ and $R^2 = 0.331$, indicating that a unit change in project planning can explain 33.1% of the variation in housing project performance. Table 4 summarizes the findings. The remaining 66.9% can be ascribed to outside variables that were not included in the research.

Table 5 ANOVA^a Results for Project Planning

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	23.114	1	23.114	55.950	.000 ^b
1 Residual	46.682	85	.431		
Total	69.796	86			
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of housing projects					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Project planning					

The results of $F = 55.950$ show that project planning has a significant impact on the performance of housing projects, demonstrating that the model fits the data well and that project planning impacts the Mavoko Sub-county housing projects' performance to a significant extent. Table 5 illustrates that the regression model accurately predicts the dependent variable at a significance level of .000, or less than 0.05.

Table 6 Regression Coefficients^a for Project Planning

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	1.379	.345		3.993	.000	.695	2.063
Project planning	.644	.086	.575	7.480	.000	.473	.814
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of housing projects							
Performance of housing projects = 1.379 + .644 (Project planning)							

According to the study's findings, adding project planning to Mavoko Sub-County has a very favourable effect on how well housing developments succeed. The results demonstrate a substantial correlation between project planning and housing project success; $p < 0.05$ ($P = 0.000$). As a result, the project planning values are significant ($t = 7.480$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that a rise in the mean project planning index should improve the performance of housing projects by a positive value of 0.644, or 64.4%. Table 6's results can be explained by the regression model that follows: Housing project performance is equal to 1.379 plus 0.644 (project planning). The model demonstrates that the performance of housing projects in Mavoko Sub-County is positively impacted by project planning.

Table 7 Model Summary for Project Planning

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.557 ^a	.310	.304	.65296
a. Predictors: (Constant), Project planning				

In a regression study, the performance of housing projects served as the dependent variable and the project team's competency served as the predictor component. As shown in Table 7, the regression analysis revealed a relationship between planning and the performance of housing that are fundamentally related, with $R = 0.557$ and $R^2 = 0.310$, respectively. A unit change in project planning can account for 31% of how differently housing projects perform from one another.

Table 8 Model Summary Multivariate Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.684 ^a	.468	.449	.58089
a. Predictors: (Constant), project planning, project funding.				

Data from 86 respondents were tested using a regression analysis with project leadership as the predictor factor, and the results show a positive correlation of $R = 0.684$ and $R^2 = 0.468$ indicated that 46.8% of the variation in the performance of housing projects could be accounted for "by variations in all the predictors used in this study, with the remaining percentage (53.2%) can be explained by the factors not considered in this study,".

Table 9 ANOVA^a Results for Model Summary

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	32.678	4	8.169	24.210	.000 ^b
1 Residual	37.118	82	.337		
Total	69.796	86			
a. DV: Performance of housing projects					
b. Predictors: project planning, and project funding					

The model fits the data well, as evidenced by the values of F = 24.210, which show that each predictor component statistically and significantly influences housing project performance that project leadership have a considerable impact on housing project success. Table 9 shows that the total regression model significantly predicts the dependent variable at the significance level of 0.000, or less than 0.05.

Table 10 Regression Coefficients^a for Multivariate Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.552	.367		1.504	.136	-.176	1.281
Project funding	.358	.118	.329	3.027	.003	.123	.592
Project planning	.307	.114	.274	2.697	.008	.081	.532
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of housing projects							
As a result, the regression model for the study is: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta^1X^1 + \beta^2X^2$							
Performance of housing projects = .552 + .358 (project funding) + .307 (project planning)							

The investigation's findings indicated that the predictor variables considerably improved the performance of housing projects at Machakos County-Mavoko Sub-County. The findings indicate that project leadership and the performance of housing projects have a significant relationship. As a result, the values of the predictor factors are statistically significant at the p.0.05 level, suggesting that housing project performance should be enhanced by raising the mean index of the predictor variables. Table 10 provides a summary of the results.

suggests that the national and county governments include stakeholders in their project financing efforts since project finance has a substantial impact on how well housing projects will perform. The performance of housing projects would be improved since the stakeholder's viewpoint would be significant in terms of finance. The findings suggest that all parties involved, including the national and county governments, should have a clear strategy on how they will finance their housing initiatives. This would guarantee that the projects are completed in the manner necessary to accomplish the stated goals. The report also advises that the national and local governments, who are stakeholders, regularly assess the different financing options.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results revealed that project financing significantly affects housing project performance, demonstrating that the model fits the data nicely and shows how project funding has a big impact on how well housing projects work. They concluded that project financing is statistically significant and influences housing project performance. The study found that project planning significantly affects housing project performance and came to the conclusion that project planning significantly affects housing project performance. As a result, the benefits of project planning are statistically significant and housing project performance and project planning are fundamentally related, indicating that a unit change in project planning can explain the variation in the performance of housing projects. The study finds that project planning significantly affects housing project performance, demonstrating that the model fits the data accurately and that project planning has a major impact on how well housing projects perform.

Since project The study concludes that funding has a major impact on housing project performance and suggests that the national and county governments involve stakeholders in their project financing activities. The study

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdullah, A., & Alshibani, A. (2022). Multi-criteria decision-making framework for selecting sustainable private partners for housing projects. *JFPC*, 27 (1), 112-140.
- [2]. Akanni, H. (2018). Strategic human resource management practices: effect on performance. *AJ EMS*, 1(2), 128-137.
- [3]. Alharbi, R. (2022). An appraisal of the early impact of COVID-19 on affordable housing finance in Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. *IJPA*, 40(3), 201-212.
- [4]. Amoah, C., & Pretorius, L. (2020). Evaluation of the impact of risk management on project performance in small construction firms in South Africa. *JEDT*, 18 (3), 611-634.
- [5]. Amoah, C., Kajimo-Shakantu, K., & van Schalkwyk, T. (2020). The empirical reality of project management failures in the construction of social housing projects in South Africa. *JFM*, 18 (4), 417-435.
- [6]. Bickman, L., & Rog, D. (2018). *Applied research design: A practical approach*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.

- [7]. Cooper, D., & Schindler, P. S. (2018). *Business Research Methods*. New Delhi: McGraw Hill.
- [8]. Crawford, L., Hobbs, J., & Turner, J. (2019). *Project Categorization Systems; PMI*. Newton Square.
- [9]. Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research Design*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [10]. Deschamps, C., & Mattijs, J. (2017). Sustainable goal setting: a large-scale case in management practice. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 66 (8), 1087-1104.
- [11]. Ferris, D. (2012). *Goal setting theory: motivation and performance*. New York: Wiley and Sons.
- [12]. Fewings, P. (2019). *Construction project management: an integrated approach*. London: Routledge.
- [13]. Gillis, W. E., Combs, J. G., & Ketchen, D. J. (2014). Using Resource-Based Theory to Help Explain Plural Form Franchising. *Entrepreneurship: Theory & Practice*, vol. 38(3), 449-472.
- [14]. Hadi, A., Ismail, S., Rani, N., & Bakar, N. (2022). *Critical Success Factors of Contractors in Affordable High-rise Public Housing in Malaysia*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [15]. Hasani, T., & O'Reilly, N. (2020). Analyzing antecedents affecting the performance of housing projects of start-up businesses. *JEEE*, 13 (1), 107-130.
- [16]. Hitt, M. A., Xu, K., & Carnes, C. M. (2016). Resource-based theory in operations management research. *JOM*, 41, 77-94.
- [17]. Iskandarani, H., Proverbs, D., & Xiao, H. (2022). Towards improving the design and planning of post-conflict housing reconstruction projects: a conceptual framework. *BEPAM*, 12(5), 902-914.
- [18]. Kalia, N., & Bhardwaj, B. (2019). Contextual and Task Performance: *RMJ*, 13 (2), 30-42.
- [19]. Kavishe, N., Jefferson, I., & Chileshe, N. (2018). An analysis of the delivery challenges influencing public-private partnership in housing projects: *ECAM*, 25 (2), 202-240.
- [20]. Kerzner, H. (2017). *Project management metrics, KPIs, and dashboards: a guide to measuring and monitoring project performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [21]. Kerzner, H., & Kerzner, H. R. (2017). *Project management*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [22]. Khan, M., Abdul-Rasid, S., Bardai, B., & Saruchi, S. (2022). The framework of affordable cooperative housing through an innovative waqf-based source of finance in Karachi. *JIABR*, 21(5), 124-132.
- [23]. Konrad, T., Wiek, A., & Barth, M. (2021). Learning processes for interpersonal competence development in project-based sustainability. *IJSHE* 22(3), 535-560.
- [24]. Kothari, C. R., & Garg, T. (2015). *Research Methodology*. New Delhi: New Age International.
- [25]. Liu, H., Ma, L., & Huang, P. (2015). Organizational complexity helps a corporation improve its performance. *JMD*, 34 (3), 340-351.
- [26]. Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2015). New Directions in Goal Setting Theory. *CDPS*, 15 (5), 265- 268.
- [27]. Muriana, C., & Vizzini, G. (2017). Project risk management: A deterministic quantitative technique for assessment and mitigation. *IJPM*, 35(3), 320-340.
- [28]. Nel, C., & Beudeker, N. (2015). *Revolution: How to create a high-performance organization*. Cape Town: VLP Publishers.
- [29]. Okuta, F., Kivaa, T., Kieti, R., & Okaka, J. (2022). Modelling the dynamic effects of macroeconomic factors on housing performance in Kenya. *IJHMA*, 29(8).
- [30]. Rashidi, A., Yong, W., Maxwell, D., & Fang, Y. (2022). Construction planning through 4D BIM-based virtual reality for light steel framing building projects. *SSBE*, 11(2).
- [31]. Saeed, M., Jiao, Y., Zahid, M., Tabassum, H., & Nauman, S. (2020). Organizational flexibility and project portfolio performance. *IJMP*, 13(7), 179-189.
- [32]. Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2018). *Research Methods for Business Students*. London: Financial Times.
- [33]. Shojaei, R., Oti-Sarpong, K., & Burgess, G. (2022). Enablers for the adoption and use of BIM in main contractor companies in the UK. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(8), 1254-1269.